

INTERLINEAR TRANSLATION

ACROSS THE MUSLIM WORLD

A Comparative Perspective

Themed Section

edited by

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A World of Words and Words for the World: Encyclopaedism and Language Learning in a 19th- century Arabic-Malay Vocabulary

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Abstract

The article looks into two manuscripts containing copies of a thematic Arabic-Malay vocabulary titled *al-Jadwal fī kalām al-ʿArab* (A list in Arabic speech). Originating in mid-19th-century West Sumatra, the manuscripts are housed in the Leiden University Library with the numbers Or. 3231(8) and 3233(2) and belong to the collection of Dutch linguist Herman Neubronner van der Tuuk (1824–1894). The vocabulary features a list of Arabic words arranged in thematic sections and provided with Malay equivalents below the line. Starting with God’s names and words describing the natural world, it proceeds to sections dealing with human society and everyday life. The article discusses the encyclopaedic nature of such an arrangement and addresses the pedagogical functions of this thematic dictionary as a tool for teaching and learning Arabic as a foreign language in the Indonesian-Malay world. Juxtaposing two versions of the same text, it questions the modes of this text’s transmission and reasons for employing an interlinear model of translation in a dictionary. Considering the divergences between the two manuscripts as well as different misspellings they contain, the article argues that the interlinear Malay translations were transmitted separately from the Arabic wordlist.

Keywords: Arabic-Malay lexicography, West Sumatra, dictionary, interlinear translation, Islamic education

Introduction

For centuries, bilingual dictionaries appear to have been an indispensable part of foreign language learning and textual translation. Some of the dictionaries listed words in alphabetical order or in order of appearance in a text (glossaries), serving as reference works for those reading and translating texts in a foreign language. Others, i.e., systematic dictionaries, or vocabularies, grouped words related to a certain field or theme and helped

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learners to build and expand their vocabulary. Surprisingly, not too long ago dictionaries of the second type were not as widely used and available as one might expect—at least, in the Indonesian-Malay world where Islam spread starting from the 13th century and Arabic was studied as the language of the Qur’an and a key to religious sciences. This article seeks to discuss a thematic Arabic-to-Malay vocabulary found in two copies from Sumatra: Leiden Or. 3231(8) and 3233(2), both belonging to the collection of Herman Neubronner van der Tuuk (1824–1894), the well-known Dutch linguist and Bible translator. Dating back to the middle of the 19th century, they represent a type of lexicographical work that is rarely found in Malay manuscript collections.

The history of Arabic-Malay lexicography has been approached by Michael Laffan² and Nico Kaptein,³ the former also touching upon the manuscripts addressed in this article. The manuscripts, i.e., Leiden Or. 3231 and 3233, are collective volumes containing several dictionaries of different types, among them alphabetical, systematic, and specialized ones. Titled *al-Jadwal fī kalām al-‘Arab* (A list in Arabic speech, or List of Arabic words), the dictionary to be discussed here is of the second type, as it is arranged in thematic sections, such as spices, animals, and body parts. The words *kitāb al-lughā* (dictionary, or literally language book) preceding the title are not part of it but rather indicate the type or genre of the book.⁴ Remaining true to the title, the dictionary is indeed a list—that of Arabic words, which are provided with Malay equivalents below the line.

In the Greco-Roman world, such lists of words arranged by semantic fields were known as *onomastica*.⁵ In the Arabic Middle East, the genre also gained currency; John Haywood defines it as “general classified vocabulary,” a type of lexicographical work that consisted of words classified by subject-matter under broad headings, or sometimes according to word-forms (in some cases both methods were mixed).⁶ However, in the Arabic-speaking world such vocabularies were monolingual. Bilingual Arabic-to-vernacular dictionaries came into play with the expansion of Islam to Persian- and Turkic-speaking regions, where the word *lūgat*, *lūgat*, or *lughat* (derived from the Arabic *al-lughā*, “language”) was used to designate a dictionary.⁷ In the same meaning, that is of a dictionary or vocabulary, (*kitāb*) *lughat* appears to have settled in the Malay language.⁸ Another feature making the Arabic-Malay

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- 2 Michael Laffan, “New Charts for the Arabic Ocean: Dictionaries as Indicators of Changing Times,” *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde* 159, no. 2–3 (2003): 351–387.
 - 3 Nico J.G. Kaptein, “Some Early Contributions to Arabic-Malay Lexicography: Sayyid ‘Uthmān of Batavia (1822–1913) as a Lexicographer,” in *Malay Images*, ed. Haji Omar A. (UPSI, 2005), 120–142.
 - 4 Jan Just Witkam, *Inventory of the Oriental Manuscripts of the Library of the University of Leiden*, vol. 4 (Ter Lugt Press, 2007), 76.
 - 5 Rolando Ferri, “The Greco-Roman World,” in *The Cambridge World History of Lexicography* (Cambridge University Press, 2019), 84, 87–88.
 - 6 John A. Haywood, *Arabic Lexicography* (Brill, 1960), 4, 111–114.
 - 7 Marek Stachowski, “The Turkic Languages and Persian to c. 1700,” in *The Cambridge World History of Lexicography* (Cambridge University Press, 2019), 223.
 - 8 Richard J. Wilkinson, *A Malay-English Dictionary* (Kelly and Walsh, 1901), 599.

vocabulary from Van der Tuuk's collection part of a wider tradition is that the words in it are written as a continuous text, which was also typical of Persian wordlists.⁹

One more wider tradition that this vocabulary appears to be part of is that of interlinear translation from Arabic into Malay or other languages of the Islamic Indonesian-Malay world. Such translations, some of them very literal and some rather interpretative, often accompany Arabic texts found in manuscripts from the region and even in later printed editions of such texts (for scholarship on the matter see works by Azyumardi Azra, Ronit Ricci, and Arif Maftuhin).¹⁰ Along with marginal annotations and commentaries, they act as paratextual elements—not being part of the main text, translations help to explain its meaning to the readers. As supplementary, optional additions, they are not always consistent and often appear occasionally throughout a text. In the manuscripts discussed in this article, however, translation is found where it appears to be unavoidable and, more than that, essential—that is, in a dictionary. A word-by-word translation, the solely possible one for a wordbook, it follows the visual pattern commonly employed by Malay translators of Arabic texts: written in a smaller script, the units of translation are placed diagonally between the lines of the source. While the genre of the text suggests that translation is indispensable, it is still visually presented as a secondary element.

Of interest from various perspectives, the vocabulary under discussion is yet to be situated in the history of Arabic-Malay lexicography. First of all, it seems to present a rare example of a handwritten Arabic-to-Malay thematic dictionary which was likely used by Malay-speaking Muslims as a learning aid in their studies of the language of Islam. Arranged in an encyclopaedic way, it provides insights into the Arabic vocabulary that was considered relevant as well as into the compilers' worldviews and mindsets. Furthermore, the two extant copies of the same dictionary allow us to look into the divergences and misspellings found in the text and discuss the modes of its transmission. And finally, the interlinear arrangement of the dictionary deserves attention, which links it with the tradition of interlinear translation in the Islamic Indonesian-Malay world and beyond. In what follows, I address the aforementioned aspects, starting with the manuscripts' provenance and description and proceeding to the structure of the vocabulary, juxtaposing the two copies, and discussing the roles of orality and interlinearity in the text's reproduction and transmission.

9 Stachowski, "The Turkic Languages and Persian," 225.

10 See Azyumardi Azra, "Naskah Terjemahan Antarbaris: Kontribusi Kreatif Dunia Islam Melayu-Indonesia," in *Sadur: Sejarah Terjemahan di Indonesia dan Malaysia*, ed. Henri Chambert-Loir (Gramedia, 2009), 435–443; Ronit Ricci, "Reading Between the Lines: A World of Interlinear Translation," *Journal of World Literature* 1, no. 1 (2016): 68–80; Ronit Ricci, "Mediating the Maulid: Interlinear Translations of the *Maulid syaraf al-anām* across the Indonesian-Malay World," *Indonesia and the Malay World* 51, no. 150 (2023): 143–164; Arif Maftuhin, "Translating the Untranslatable. The Jalālayn Learning as a Translation Practice," *Indonesia and the Malay World* 51, no. 151 (2024): 279–303.

Van der Tuuk's Vocabularies

Among the manuscript collection of Van der Tuuk housed in the Leiden University Library, there are three collective volumes with the subsequent numbers Or. 3231, 3232 and 3233. They contain various texts most of which deal with the Arabic language, including Arabic-Malay and Arabic-Javanese dictionaries and texts on Arabic grammar.¹¹ Leiden Or. 3232 is copied by Van der Tuuk himself, while Or. 3233 contains marginal notes by his hand. Or. 3233 comprises three Arabic-Malay dictionaries, of which two duplicate those found in Or. 3231: Or. 3233(1) is the same as Or. 3231(6), while Or. 3233(2) is another copy of Or. 3231(8). According to Petrus Voorhoeve, “both volumes were copied about the middle of the 19th century, Or. 3233 in Sumatra. This may also be the place of origin of Or. 3231.”¹²

If this is indeed the case, the manuscripts must have been acquired by Van der Tuuk sometime between 1851 and 1857 during his travels in western and northern Sumatra. Early in 1851, the linguist, who had been commissioned by the Dutch Bible Society (*Nederlands Bijbelgenootschap*, NBG) to study the Toba Batak language and ultimately translate the Bible into it, embarked on his voyage from Java and arrived at Padang, a port in the Minangkabau lands and the seat of the colonial government of Sumatra's West Coast.¹³ From there Van der Tuuk continued north to Tapanuli region, where he settled in the coastal town of Sibolga in mid-1851. In late 1851 or early 1852, he moved further north to Barus, also a coastal town, and stayed there until April 1857, when he travelled on foot all the way back to Padang and soon left West Sumatra for good. During his residence in Barus, the scholar undertook several trips into the interior of the island, i.e., to the still independent Toba Batak and Mandailing lands.¹⁴ With the help of his local informants, whom he also hired as scribes for copying manuscripts and writing down oral texts, Van der Tuuk accumulated a collection of materials that he later bequeathed to the University of Leiden.

The Arabic-Malay vocabularies were apparently among these texts, although it remains unknown where exactly the two manuscripts come from—as the scholar did not keep records

11 See Edwin P. Wieringa, *Catalogue of Malay and Minangkabau Manuscripts in the Library of Leiden University and Other Collections in the Netherlands*, vol. 2 (Leiden University Library, 2007), 79–83; Witkam, *Inventory of the Oriental Manuscripts*, 75–77; also Petrus Voorhoeve, “Indonesische handschriften in de Universiteitsbibliotheek te Leiden,” *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde* 108, no. 3 (1952): 216; Voorhoeve, *Handlist of Arabic Manuscripts in the Library of the University of Leiden and Other Collections in the Netherlands* (Leiden University Press, 1980), 160, 417–418; Teuku Iskandar, *Catalogue of Malay, Minangkabau, and South Sumatran Manuscripts in the Netherlands*, vol. 1, (Documentatiebureau Islam-Christendom, 1999), 120–121.

12 Voorhoeve, *Handlist of Arabic Manuscripts*, 418.

13 Toba Batak are an ethnic group residing in the hinterland of North Sumatra in the vicinity of Lake Toba. At the time of arrival of European Christian missionaries in the 19th century, they had not been impacted by Islamisation and retained their animistic beliefs. Minangkabau are an ethnic group inhabiting the highlands of western Sumatra. In the mid-19th century, the majority of them already professed Islam.

14 Kees Groenboer, *Een vorst onder de taalgeleerden: Herman Neubronner van der Tuuk, taalafgevaardigde voor Indië van het Nederlandsch Bijbelgenootschap 1847–1873* (KITLV, 2002), 12–15. Mandailing are a predominantly Muslim Batak ethnic group residing in South Tapanuli.

of places where he acquired his materials.¹⁵ In his last, posthumously published work Van der Tuuk mentions an incomplete Arabic-Malay dictionary, apparently Or. 3233(2), that “comes from the Padang Highlands and is here and there Minangkabau-ish.”¹⁶ Or. 3233(2) indeed contains a colophon indicating its Minangkabau origins (f. 56v), which reads as follows: “written by a person from Bayang, son of Tuanku in Jambak bearing the title Fakih Sultan at the time of building the surau in the village of Lubuk Gambir” (*Yang menyurat dia orang Bayang anak Tuanku di Jambak yang bergelar Fakih Sultan tatkala berbuat surau dalam karya Lubuk Gambir adanya*).¹⁷ Bayang is a coastal town south of Padang to the north of which a village called Lubuk Gambir can be found, while Jambak refers to a smaller unit within the village named after the Minangkabau clan that the land belonged to.¹⁸ In any case, the circumstance that the manuscript was copied in Bayang area does not imply that this was where Van der Tuuk acquired it (likely bought, as the colophon also mentions a price—two rials). Or. 3231(8) does not have a colophon, and very little can be assumed about its origins. Both manuscripts could have been acquired either during the linguist’s overland journey to Padang, in Padang, Sibolga, or in Barus, where a local chief named Tuanku Sutan Ibrahim used to lend Van der Tuuk some of the Malay and Minangkabau texts that he owned.¹⁹

Van der Tuuk’s interest in Arabic-Malay dictionaries reflects his research methods and interests as a linguist and lexicographer from different perspectives, among them his background in Arabic studies, his lifelong interest in Malay and unfulfilled plans to compile a new dictionary of this language,²⁰ and his preference of the written word over the spoken one. First and foremost, Van der Tuuk was “a lifelong collector of words, in as many Indonesian languages as he could lay his hands on.”²¹ Although his primary mission in Sumatra was to study the Toba Batak language, he also used this opportunity to broaden his knowledge of local Malay and Minangkabau. An insight into the linguist’s early engagement with the Arabic-Malay dictionaries he had collected can be found in his letter to the Bible Society, with which he maintained regular correspondence from Barus:

These languages are rich and poor, as they like to say: rich in concrete words and poor in abstract ones. Neither Malay nor Batak has a word for *animal* in general, and I have often seen a native laughing at me because I applied *bienatang* to a worm. Meanwhile, he has a name for the smallest reptile. This is the case with all peoples who are semi-

15 Marije Plomp, “Never-neverland Revisited: Malay Adventure Stories: With an Annotated Edition and Translation of the Malay Story of Bahram Syah” (Ph.D. Dissertation, Leiden University, 2014), 58.

16 Herman N. van der Tuuk, *Eene aanvulling der Maleische woordenboeken* (’s-Gravenhage: Nijhoff, 1894), 50; see also Wieringa, *Catalogue of Malay and Minangkabau Manuscripts*, 81–83.

17 Among the Minangkabau, Tuanku (or Tuangku) is a title of a religious leader or scholar, while *surau* is a term for Islamic school. For Islamic education and translation practice in *surau*, see Fadhli Lukman’s article in the present issue.

18 I thank Pramono for his help in identifying the place.

19 Plomp, “Never-neverland Revisited,” 43.

20 See Cornelis D. Grijns, “Van der Tuuk and the Study of Malay,” *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde* 152, no. 3 (1996); Andries Teeuw, “Van der Tuuk as Lexicographer,” *Archipel*, no. 51 (1996): 118, 122.

21 Teeuw, “Van der Tuuk as Lexicographer.” 113.

civilized, and it is also the reason why, when they come into contact with foreigners, they use foreign words to express abstract ideas, while when they attain without these foreigners the requisite degree of civilisation at which the expression of abstracts becomes necessary, a concrete word gets elevated to an abstract. Isn't it to be explained in this way that *dog* (in our language the name of a type of dog) means in English *a dog* in general? At the same time, *hound* in English is the name of a type of dog, while for us *hond* is the general word. The Arabic-Malay dictionaries have elevated concrete words to general ones; thus I find *bienatang* (wild animal) given as *animal* and *kara* (certain small long-tailed monkey) as the general name for *monkey*, simply because the writers did not find general words for *animal* and *monkey* in Malay. The compilers of these dictionaries were probably Malays civilized by Arabs, because the dictionaries provide very few words taken from Arabic as equivalents of the Arabic words to be explained, which would have been the case if the authors were Arab. (*Aan Bijbelgenootschap, Baroes 27-3-1854*)²²

Van der Tuuk approached these dictionaries, which he continued to consult throughout his life, primarily from the perspective of historical linguistics. His last treatise dealt with Malay lexicography, and in it the scholar addressed one of the vocabularies (Or. 3233(2), as mentioned above) as a source on Minangkabau language and its Agam dialect, also pointing to the discrepancies between Arabic words and their vernacular translations.²³ In his lexicographical studies, Van der Tuuk used handwritten dictionaries along with multiple other manuscripts that he eagerly collected. Those were texts of most diverse content, as the scholar did not see any literary value in them²⁴ but approached them as mere sources of lexical information. Although oral conversations with native speakers constituted a substantial part of his fieldwork, Van der Tuuk considered written materials the only reliable basis for describing a language. A “conviction of his, to which he adhered also in the daily practice of his lexicographical work in the field, was that words should be studied in their syntactic context and that therefore written texts were an essential tool for a lexicographer. Consequently, the hunter of words automatically became a collector of manuscripts.”²⁵

These Van der Tuuk used to either purchase or commission as copies by local scribes; sometimes he copied texts himself in his sloppy handwriting—as is the case with the Arabic-Javanese dictionary found in Leiden Or. 3232. Unlike his materials from Bali, most of the Malay manuscripts in the scholar's collection were bought rather than copied on order.²⁶ In an article written during his residence in Barus, Van der Tuuk expresses his views on the essential role of texts as recorded by the speakers of the language:

Consultation of the natives about their language is very risky and may be useful only for verifying the pronunciation; the meaning of words is better learned from an

²² Quoted in Groenboer, *Een vorst onder de taalgeleerden*, 203.

²³ Tuuk, *Eene aanvulling der Maleische woordenboeken*, 50–52.

²⁴ Plomp, “Never-neverland Revisited,” 21.

²⁵ Teeuw, “Van der Tuuk as Lexicographer,” 130.

²⁶ Grijns, “Van der Tuuk and the Study of Malay,” 368.

assiduous application to the study of Malay writers than from speaking to people with insufficient education to understand questions about linguistic problems.²⁷

Another consideration of his was apparently an unwillingness to put himself beyond the reach of scholarly criticism, as written sources could serve as proof for the his arguments.²⁸ Handwritten texts formed the basis of Van der Tuuk's dictionaries, and they have come down to us not only as the linguist's heritage and evidence of his research methodology and sources, but also as witnesses of West Sumatra's 19th-century history and cultural milieu, as well as insights into its Islamic education practices, of which teaching and learning Arabic constituted an indispensable part.

Apart from purely linguistic inquiries, many questions could be asked in respect of the Arabic-Malay vocabulary preserved in two copies by virtue of Van der Tuuk's travels and studies. Who were the compilers of this wordlist and what audiences did they aim at? Might it have been written by an autodidact for private use, or was it rather composed by a teacher for students, or by an Arab sheikh for Malay learners of Arabic?²⁹ Were the Arabic words and their vernacular translations written down by the same scribe and at the same time, copied from a written source or orally dictated? What informed the selection of words included in the vocabulary—were they considered useful for a person aspiring to *speak* Arabic (for instance, planning a journey to Mecca), or for those reading and translating Islamic texts, the words having been extracted from those very texts rather than from the author's memory? These are far from all the questions that arise. Not all of them can be answered drawing upon the two copies at our disposal, therefore in what follows I will address only some of these questions.

Naming Things, Structuring the World

In Leiden Or. 3231, *al-Jadwal fi kalām al-ʿArab* occupies some 80 pages (ff. 44v–4r). The collective volume also contains several other texts by different copyists that would be helpful to a learner of Arabic, i.e., three other Arabic-Malay vocabularies and two texts on Arabic grammar. Only one of the vocabularies is arranged alphabetically (Or. 3231(6)), while the other three are systematic: Or. 3231(7) and (8) list words in thematic sections, while Or. 3231(9) deals with only one topic, which is *fiqh*. Or. 3231(8) is written by a somewhat sloppy hand in black ink; unlike other manuscripts constituting the volume, it has no rubrication in red. The sections are largely untitled, mostly marked by an overlined word “section” (*faṣl*), so that the logic of the compiler can only be guessed from the contents. Vocalized Arabic words are put one after another in a line, little space being left between them, while their

27 Herman N. van der Tuuk, “lets over de Hoog-Maleische bijbelvertaling,” *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land en Volkenkunde* 5, no. 1 (1856): 179. Quoted in Grijns, “Van der Tuuk and the Study of Malay,” 358. On Van der Tuuk's methodology in this regard, see also Teeuw, “Van der Tuuk as Lexicographer,” 121.

28 Teeuw, 116.

29 As it appears to be the case with a similar systematic vocabulary, Or. 3231(7), which is said to have been compiled by an imam for his brethren (see Wieringa, *Catalogue of Malay and Minangkabau Manuscripts*, 2007: 81; Witkam, *Inventory of the Oriental Manuscripts*, 2007: 76).

Malay equivalents are written in smaller script diagonally below the line. The interlinear translation appears rather terse, only one translation option provided for each word.

On the first page (f. 44r, see Fig. 1), the text identifies itself as *Kitāb al-lughā al-jadwal fī kalām al-‘Arab*, while in the colophon (f. 4v) a different title appears, that is *al-Kitāb al-lughā al-jadwal fī bayān al-taṣrīf* (The dictionary [entitled] “A list in the clarification of morphology”). In both cases *al-jadwal* (list) is misspelled as *al-jadwāl*, which might as well be a misspelling of the plural form *al-jadāwil*, as on f. 44r we find *al-jadwāl* after a numeral (*thalāthat al-jadwāl*), while in the next sentence the singular form *al-jadwal* is spelled correctly three times in a row. If the latter is the case, the title should be rather translated as “Lists in Arabic speech.” The actual wordlist is preceded with a *basmala* and traditional doxology, followed by a reference to unspecified ‘*ulamā*’ who had said that “language is soil and knowledge is vegetation” (apparently referring to the hadith found on the previous page, f. 45r) as well as that “language is the key to sciences” (f. 4v). Written in Arabic, the introductory part is also provided with interlinear Malay translation.

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From this the compiler proceeds to explain the structure of the vocabulary, which is divided into three major parts (or lists) according to a grammatical principle: particles (*jadwal al-ḥarf*), nouns or “names” (*jadwal al-ism*, which also includes adjectives and numerals), and verbs (*jadwal al-fi‘l*). These larger “chapters,” just as their sub-sections, are indiscriminately called *faṣl* throughout the text. In the introduction, however, the three large sections are referred to as lists, which might indeed explain why the title of the vocabulary should be read rather as “Lists” than “A list.” By the end of the text, the handwriting seems to become more roundish and thorough—as if a different scribe has stepped in, so that the colophon appears to be written by the same hand as the wordlist entitled *al-Lughat al-fiqh* (ungrammatical Arabic for “a dictionary of juridical terms”) that follows it (Or. 3231(9)). Laffan suggests that this latter text was added by the scribe as a supplement to the preceding vocabulary, i.e., Or. 3231(8).³⁰

The second copy of the same dictionary is also part of a collective volume, that is Leiden Or. 3233, in which it is found between two other Arabic-Malay dictionaries arranged alphabetically. One of these two, Or. 3233(1), is the same text as Or. 3231(6). Two of the three texts in Or. 3233, therefore, duplicate those in Or. 3231. Unlike Or. 3231, Or. 3233 contains notes by Van der Tuuk’s hand in the margins. The systematic vocabulary Or. 3233(2) occupies 54 pages (ff. 30v-56v) and is missing the beginning—this is only evident from the fact that it commences with the words found on page 6 of Or. 3231(8) (f. 42v), as the beginning of this second copy of the dictionary is clearly marked with a *basmala* in place of a title. The incompleteness of the text, which disconcerted Van der Tuuk,³¹ thus was likely due not to missing first pages but to an incomplete source manuscript at the copyist’s disposal. No title for the text is provided, neither on the first page nor in the above mentioned colophon that attributes the copy to a Minangkabau scribe from Bayang.

The handwriting in this copy is generally finer than in Or. 3231(8); unlike in the latter, Arabic words have no diacritics added, while the sections are highlighted in red. The number

30 Laffan, “New Charts for the Arabic Ocean,” 353.

31 Tuuk, *Eene aanvulling der Maleische woordenboeken*, 52.

of lines on the page is nine, as opposed to seven in Or. 3231(8). In the margins, pencil notes and marks by the hand of Van der Tuuk appear. Some of these are catchwords in Dutch indicating categories that are treated in the unnamed *faṣl*, e.g., gold, gems, tools, animals, body parts and clothes. As in the other copy, Malay translations of the Arabic words are provided below the line. In both manuscripts translations for some words are missing, while for words that seem to have been considered synonyms, they tend to be replaced with the letter *mīm*. In Or. 3233(2), the layout appears neater than in Or. 3231(8), which is arranged in a less coherent way, interlinear translations overflowing to the margins and additional words and annotations inserted here and there. Altogether, Or. 3231(8) with its messy writing, vocalized Arabic, and no rubrication leaves an impression that it was once used in a teaching and learning process. Or. 3233(2), on the other hand, appears to be a more thorough copy of a manuscript similar to Or. 3231(8), though it once served as study material too—not for a surau student but for a Dutch linguist. Hereafter I refer to Or. 3231(8) as the first copy and to Or. 3233(2) as the second copy of the vocabulary.

As has been mentioned, the vocabulary is divided into three major chapters according to a morphological principle: particles, nouns (*al-ism*), and verbs. Within the chapter on nouns, thematic arrangement is applied. It takes an encyclopaedic form, commencing with sections on names (or attributes) of God, religious, epistemological and abstract terms, and then proceeding to words describing the physical world: those for land and sky; geographical notions; inanimate phenomena and materials; spices and aromatics; food and drink; vessels and household utensils; diseases; plants and their parts; water and fish; animals and insects; body parts; categories of people; clothes and furnishings. The encyclopaedism of the wordlist appears rather intuitive, although it might have been inspired to a certain extent by post-classical Arabic cosmologies such as *‘Ajā’ib al-makhlūqāt* (The Wonders of Creation) by Zakariyā al-Qazwīnī (c.1203–1283), which tend to zoom in from the celestial to the terrestrial. Or it could have been inspired by some treatises of the same genre, such as the systematic Persian-Arabic dictionary by al-Zamakhsharī (1075–1144) that combines grammatical and thematic arrangements and groups nouns in sections beginning with time and sky and moving on to earthly subjects.³² Commencing with God’s names and words describing the natural world and proceeding to sections dealing with human society and everyday life, *al-Jadwal fī kalām al-‘Arab* follows this pattern. Assembling the elusive foreign words in logically arranged sections, the compilers unwittingly describe the world around them in an encyclopaedic and largely intuitive way, one that had been likely informed by their cultural background. In this regard, the vocabulary reflects not only language learning practices at the time, but also Malay Muslims’ worldviews and mindsets.

Having listed God’s attributes, the vocabulary proceeds to the next *faṣl* which commences with *al-ḥayāt* (life) and contains words that can be vaguely described as general terms, e.g., power, desire, speech, sleep, entrance and exit, increase and decrease. This is followed by sections dealing with celestial phenomena (sun, moon, stars, clouds, rain, wind, etc.) and the cardinal points; geographical terms (e.g., mountain, plain, forest, village, town, road, house), metals and minerals; medicine and plants. The first copy (ff. 36r–34v) contains sections on flora, spices and aromatics, drinks and cups, tools, and diseases that are missing from the

³² Haywood, *Arabic Lexicography*, 118.

second copy (see f. 35v). After these come lists of words for water bodies (sea, river, spring); fish and aquatic animals; and finally land animals—this latter section commencing with the word *al-hayawān* (animal) that is translated to Malay as *segala yang hidup* (lit. everything that lives). Amidst the reptiles, a mythical creature has crept in, i.e., *tinnīn/naga* (dragon). Some of the animal species listed are found both in the Middle East and the Malay archipelago, some are not: among the latter are camels, lions, and particular species of birds.³³

Finding no equivalents to such animals' names in Malay, the translators opt for conveying them with words for similar animals. For instance, *al-hudhud* (hoopoe) is translated as *merak* (peacock)—apparently due to the feather crests on both birds' heads. This word for some reason attracted the attention of Van der Tuuk, who notes “*hudhud*” in the margin of the page (see Fig. 2).³⁴ *Al-asad* (lion) is translated as *harimau* (tiger), *al-dhi'b* (wolf) as *harimau akar* (clouded leopard), and *al-nimr* (the actual tiger) as *harimau kecil* (small tiger) in the second copy and as another *harimau akar* in the first one. The latter case also demonstrates that, unlike the Arabic words that differ between the two copies only in spelling (misspellings occur widely in both versions of the vocabulary), their Malay translations occasionally differ in content—yet most of the translation choices still overlap. Also, as was pointed out by Van der Tuuk, Arabic loanwords are barely used in the translation—although the borrowed word for lion, *asada*, for example, had been in use in literary Malay since the 17th century.³⁵

Humans find themselves at the very beginning of the fauna section where they precede cattle and are classified according to their gender, age, and social roles: men and women, free and enslaved, old and young, kings, ministers, and generals.³⁶ A section dealing with women also appears further in the vocabulary, after the lists of words for animals and human body parts. Women are divided into maids, brides, widows, prostitutes; young, middle aged, and old; married and not.³⁷ Misspellings make some of the Arabic words unrecognizable, so that only the Malay translations allow for their identification: for instance, *al-qahba* (“prostitute,” translated into Malay as *perempuan jahat*, “bad woman,” in both copies) is spelled as *al-fujuba* in the first copy and in the second one as *al-tahiya*. The following section provides a variety of kinship terms, beginning with a distinction between a *al-qarīb* (“relative,” translated into Malay as *keluarga*, “family”) and *al-ajnabī* (stranger) or *al-gharīb* (foreigner). *Al-ajnabī* is translated as *orang asing* (foreigner) in the first copy and as *orang lain* (other person) in the second one, while *al-gharīb* is conveyed as *orang dagang* (trader)—a translation choice reflecting the most historically common context for encounters with foreigners in the archipelago. The second copy also provides two Arabic synonyms for “relative” that are absent from the first one, demonstrating that the latter is not always the more complete version of the vocabulary.

33 See ff. 33v–31v in the first copy and ff. 36v–38r in the second one.

34 F. 38r of the second copy.

35 Tom G. Hoogervorst, “Seventeenth-century Malay Wordlists and Their Potential for Etymological Scholarship,” *Wacana, Journal of the Humanities of Indonesia* 25, no. 3 (2024): 543.

36 See f. 33r in the first copy, f. 36v in the second.

37 Ff. 29v (copy 1) and 39v (copy 2).

The section proceeds with words related to nobility and lineage that are followed by a list of kinship terms such as father, mother, son, grandson, and so on.³⁸ In the second copy, the translator does not differentiate between maternal and paternal aunts and uncles, conveying the four Arabic words indiscriminately as *mamak lelaki/perempuan*—quite an unidiomatic phrasing for uncle/aunt, that can be literally translated as “male uncle” and “female uncle.” Also, while the word *mamak* (maternal uncle) can sometimes be used to refer to a maternal aunt, it is not known to be applied to paternal relatives.³⁹ In the first copy, the translation attempts more precision but still does not avoid confusion: *al-‘amm* (paternal uncle) is translated as *mamak saudara bapak* (*mamak* father’s sibling), *al-‘amma* (paternal aunt) as *mamak saudara ibu* (*mamak* mother’s sibling), *al-khāl* (maternal uncle) as *saudara ibu laki-laki* (mother’s brother), and *al-khāla* (maternal aunt) as *saudara ibu perempuan* (mother’s sister). This confusion around kinship terms, especially in relation to maternal and paternal uncles, the former (*mamak*) being the central figure in the Minangkabau kinship system, might testify that the compilers of the vocabulary were more likely Malay than Minangkabau. While Minangkabau only recognize maternal uncle as *mamak*, both copies of the vocabulary use the word *mamak* to translate “paternal uncle” from Arabic, and the first copy does not translate the actual *mamak*, i.e., *al-khāl*, as *mamak* at all.

The absence in Malay of different words for sister and brother, aunt and uncle, daughter and son forces the translators to add gender markers (*perempuan*, “female”/*laki-laki*, “male”) here and there, complicating for them the already challenging task of explaining the variety of Arabic kinship terms with the few Malay words at their disposal. However, as elsewhere throughout the vocabulary, the translators still tend to opt for (inaccurate) translations rather than lengthier explanations. The words for family members are followed by those describing other kinds of interpersonal relationships, e.g., lover, friend, enemy, competitor, neighbor, compatriot, and drinking companion.

From people the vocabulary moves to their everyday life, rich and poor, and the objects that play part in it. Starting from clothing, it proceeds to household textiles, furnishings, and jewelry, *al-hijāb* being placed not among veils and headscarves but among curtains and carpets (see Fig. 3 and 4).⁴⁰ Among the face and head covers the vocabulary lists *al-burqa‘*, translated as *tutup muka* (face cover); *al-niqāb*, *ikat muka* (face band); and *al-‘iṣāba* (head band, turban), translated as *ikat kepala* (head band), as well as three words for women’s veil—*al-khimār*, *al-miqna‘a*, and *al-qinā‘*—that are translated as *mahkota* (crown, headgear). Different types of textiles are also listed (taffeta, brocade, satin), for which the translators find no Malay equivalents and describe as *kain sutra* (silk cloth). The following sections of the noun chapter of the vocabulary (*jadwal al-ism*) deal with abstract nouns, colors, adjectives, numerals, and nouns related to quantity, the pattern of its arrangement gradually changing back from thematic to grammatical.

Next to nothing being known about the authors, audiences, and reasons for compiling *al-Jadwal fi kalām al-‘Arab*, the vocabulary itself appears to be the only source to draw upon.

38 Ff. 29v–28r (1) and 39v–40v (2).

39 I am grateful to Fadhli Lukman for his insights regarding the matter.

40 Ff. 28r–27r (1) and 41r–41v (2).

The numerous misspellings and inaccurate translations of Arabic words seem to indicate that the wordlist was unlikely to have been written by native Arabic-speakers. As has been suggested by Van der Tuuk, albeit on other grounds, the compilers were apparently Malay (or still possibly Minangkabau?). The providing of as many synonyms as possible and the inclusion of some rather rare and infrequently used Arabic words leave an impression that this dictionary is not a pilgrim's wordbook aiming to build an active vocabulary for speaking Arabic, but rather an aid for a bookish learner of language, a reader and translator of Arabic texts. As reading and translating Islamic texts was the major method of teaching and learning Arabic in the Indonesian-Malay world at the time,⁴¹ the words constituting the dictionary might have been collected from these very texts. Grouping them thematically would facilitate memorization and shape a passive vocabulary allowing the student to recognize these words when encountered in another text of similar genre. The translators' frequent choices in favour of inaccurate single-word equivalents rather than explanatory translations apparently worked towards the same goal, as such words would be easier to insert into the resulting translated text in Malay.

Interlinear translations, which often accompany Arabic texts in manuscripts from the Indonesian-Malay world, tend to allow a considerable degree of exegesis: they are often rather interpretative and can be longer and more detailed than the source.⁴² In the Arabic-Malay vocabulary in question, this does not seem to be the case, its didactic encyclopaedism manifesting itself in the thematic arrangement but not in explaining the cultural and natural realities of the Middle East. This absence of cultural translation, in its modern understanding, can be alternatively described as cultural translation of a different kind: an approach that highlights not the differences between the Arabic heartlands and the Malay Archipelago but the unity and uniformity of the Islamic world. Replacing the unfamiliar with the familiar, the vocabulary brings the language of the scripture and texts written in it closer to Malay-speaking Muslims. Employing an interlinear layout for a dictionary, a work of a different genre than the narrative texts that were usually provided with translations below the line, encompasses *al-Jadwal fi kalām al-ʿArab* within the long tradition of interlinear translation from Arabic and reception of Arabic texts in the Indonesian-Malay world. The reasons why this layout was chosen might have to do with the modes of such texts' transmission—on which juxtaposing the two copies of the same vocabulary sheds some light.

Misspellings, Discrepancies, and Where They Come From

Comparing the copies of *al-Jadwal fi kalām al-ʿArab* at our disposal reveals divergences between the two—both in the Arabic and Malay parts of the text. However, these discrepancies are of a different nature: while the Arabic wordlists in the two manuscripts differ in terms of completeness and (mis)spelling, their Malay translations vary in content.

41 See Aglaia Iankovskaia, "Reading Arabic in Sumatra. Interlinear Translation in Didactic Contexts," *Indonesia and the Malay World* 52, no. 153 (2024): 221–242.

42 See Aglaia Iankovskaia, "Between Translation and Commentary: An Interlinear Text from the Collection of Snouck Hurgronje," *Archipel*, no. 106 (2023): 89–124.

Looking into the two versions of first Arabic and then Malay components of the bilingual text, that is the vocabulary, also seems to reveal that these two parts are not necessarily inseparable and they could have been transmitted at different times and in different ways.

The Arabic wordlists in the two copies mostly overlap (except for some missing sections and words); however, the spelling of words differs to a considerable extent. Both vocabularies contain misspellings, which sometimes make the Arabic words hardly recognizable. These misspellings appear to be distributed between the two manuscripts in relatively equal proportion: some words are spelled correctly in Or. 3233(2) and misspelled in Or. 3231(8), and vice versa. Indeed, the two versions of the vocabulary help a modern reader to decipher them both. Most of the misspellings appear to be of a graphical nature, e.g., letters of similar shapes are confused or dots misplaced, which apparently indicates that the manuscripts are not directly related and the wordlists in them have travelled different paths of corruption in the process of recopying. But it might have not only been recopying written texts that contributed to this corruption.

For instance, in the section dealing with clothes and textiles (see Fig. 3 and 4), there appears a confusing word spelled as *dāl-ḥā-rā-yā-dād* in the first copy and *dāl-ḥā-rā-ṣād* in the second one, which can be read as *dahrīd* or possibly *dahrīṣ* (as the second copy provides no diacritics). Such a word does not seem to be found in dictionaries of Arabic, but its interlinear Malay translation appears to give a clue to what it might have originally been. Below the line, this word is translated as *suji baju* (shirt embroidery). Meanwhile there is an Arabic word for embroidery that could have sounded similarly to *dahrīṣ* to a non-native Arabic speaker, that is *taṭrīz*, as well as another word, *takhrīm*, that could have possibly transformed into *dahrīṣ* as a result of two stages of corruption, phonetical and graphical—the final *mīm* having been misinterpreted by a copyist as *ṣād*. If either of the two is the case, this seems to suggest that the history of reproduction of the text included both written and oral transmission, i.e., at different points in time the vocabulary might have been copied from a manuscript and written down by dictation.

In the Arabic lines of the vocabulary, such possible traces of oral transmission still appear to be rather scarce. The majority of misspellings are those a copyist could produce due to inattention or unclear handwriting in the earlier manuscript, while the scribe's relatively fine hand, especially in the second version, suggests that the wordlist was copied without much haste from a written source. This, however, does not seem to be the case for the interlinear Malay translation, which is in both cases scribbled between the lines in a less accurate manner and might have not been copied at the same time as the Arabic text. Besides the sloppiness of the handwriting, there is another feature pointing to the different life paths of the Arabic and Malay parts of the vocabulary. Although the Malay translations of the Arabic words in the two manuscripts are largely identical, they do not overlap entirely, and the differences do not seem to result from recopying. For example, the Arabic word *al-sundus* (taffeta, thin silk textile) is translated in the first version as *kain sutra yang nipis* (thin silk fabric) and in the second one as just *kain* (cloth, fabric); and *al-biṭāna* (lining) as *lapis baju* (shirt lining) and *luar baju* (outer layer of a shirt), respectively. The translation discrepancies found in sections dealing with animals and kinship terms have been already mentioned above.

Corrupted as it is, the Arabic wordlist in the vocabulary still appears to be a more stable part of the text than the Malay translations. The spelling differences between the two manuscripts seem to be unintentional and rather result from the multiple stages of thorough

but not flawless recopying by non-native Arabic speakers. The variety in translations, on the other hand, appears to be more voluntary, which might reflect the fluid character of interlinear translation as a practice and the role of an oral element in its transmission. These observations seem to correspond to the fluidity of interlinear translation as it manifests itself in other bilingual manuscripts from the Indonesian-Malay world and from Sumatra in particular.⁴³ The majority of such manuscripts contain Arabic texts that were part of traditional Islamic education in the region and used to be studied with a teacher whose oral remarks were scribbled by students between the lines of their copies. As a result of this practice, the Arabic source texts (*matn*) in these manuscripts tend to be less variable than their Malay or other interlinear translations. Providing that the Arabic-Malay vocabulary under discussion might have been once used in a similar study and transmission process, the translation differences between the two versions could result from a teacher's reinterpretation in the classroom or a student's hastiness in writing down the translations.

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Yet the main text, i.e., the Arabic wordlist, was most likely copied from a written source before being brought to the classroom or study circle, its transmission might have also involved oral elements—to which the few phonetical misspellings in it seem to testify. Little is known about scribal practices of manuscript production and reproduction in 19th-century Sumatra, but there is some evidence scattered around the Indonesian-Malay region and across centuries. Dick van der Meij reports Merle Ricklefs' accounts of his observations in 1960s Yogyakarta, where production of a manuscript was a group activity “done with one person writing while singing the text, another (or others) singing along or singing from an original being copied, others joining in with comments and suggestions, and so on.” Checking the newly made copy also involved singing and working in pairs.⁴⁴ This latter practice of collating a copy with the original, one scribe reading the source manuscript aloud and another checking the text in the copy, is also mentioned as early as 1603 in a treatise composed in Aceh, i.e., Bukhari al-Jauhari's *Tāj al-salāṭīn*.⁴⁵

Commenting on Merle Ricklefs' observations in Java, Van der Meij notes that “this is very interesting information as it may have serious implications for the philological method. It is not that a scribe copies the text from a manuscript in front of him, and thus he or she does not necessarily use the same letters used in the exemplar. An oral layer lies between the exemplar and the copy.”⁴⁶ Such an “oral layer” could indeed explain some of the misspellings found in the two manuscripts of *al-Jadwal fī kalām al-‘Arab*. Copying a manuscript was not always a group activity, but even as an individual one it could involve oral practices, e.g., the

43 See Aglaiia Iankovskaia, “On ‘Hanging Meaning’ and Its Transmission. Tracing a Didactic Poem from Aceh,” *Archipel*, no. 107 (2024): 119–138.

44 Dick van der Meij, *Indonesian Manuscripts from the Islands of Java, Madura, Bali and Lombok* (Brill, 2017), 22.

45 Vladimir I. Braginsky, “Malay Scribes on Their Craft and Audience (With Special Reference to the Description of the Reading Assembly by Safirin bin Usman Fadli),” *Indonesia and the Malay World* 30, no. 86 (2002): 37–38.

46 Van der Meij, *Indonesian Manuscripts from the Islands of Java*, 22.

scribe simultaneously reading the text aloud and committing it to writing: “the mouth is reading while the hand is writing.”⁴⁷

Juxtaposing the two copies of the Arabic-Malay vocabulary seems to demonstrate that they are not directly related, apparently stemming from some other copies that were circulating in the region at the time, and that they both contain traces of oral practices having been involved in their transmission. It seems also likely that the Arabic and Malay components of the text were not transmitted at the same time and in the same place—which the vocabulary’s interlinear layout might attest to. In Malay manuscript culture, interlinear translations were viewed as paratextual, optional elements rather than parts of the main text and were often added to the *matn* as a second layer. In many manuscripts, such translations are not complete and tend to end abruptly after the first few pages—as if the translator had given up the task, or rather only part of the text had been studied by a student with a teacher. Evidence of a similar treatment of lexicographical texts can be found in a manuscript of another Arabic-Malay vocabulary which Van der Tuuk cataloged in the collection of the Royal Asiatic Society after his visit to London in 1865:

An Arabic-Malay Dictionary. Under each Arabic word the corresponding Malay is written. The last seven pages are not filled up with the Malay. I possess a complete copy, and a fragment of another work of the same kind.⁴⁸

This manuscript is RAS Raffles Malay 75 (D) that is still housed in the library of the Royal Asiatic Society.⁴⁹ As has been noted both by Van der Tuuk and later catalogers,⁵⁰ its last pages are lacking Malay equivalents for the Arabic words (see Fig. 5). This possibly indicates that compilers of such vocabularies considered translation optional rather than an indispensable part of their treatises. In this light, the Arabic-Malay vocabulary discussed in this article should not be viewed as a dictionary in its usual sense, but rather as a wordlist provided with an interlinear translation. This is indeed how this text identifies itself in the title—“A list of Arabic words.”

Why Interlinear? In Lieu of a Conclusion

Repeatedly labeled by its European collector and later scholars and catalogers as a “dictionary” or “vocabulary,” *al-Jadwal fi kalām al-‘Arab* does not entirely correspond to the (relatively modern) idea of a bilingual lexicographical work comprising words in the source language and their explicit translations to the target one. Neither does it seem to be what it

47 Braginsky, “Malay Scribes on Their Craft,” 39–40.

48 Herman N. van der Tuuk, “Short Account of the Malay Manuscripts Belonging to the Royal Asiatic Society,” *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society of Great Britain and Ireland* 2, no. 1 (1866): 124.

49 A digital copy of this manuscript is available online at <https://royalasiaticcollections.org/raffles-malay-75-fragment-of-malay-laws/> (accessed on 4 May 2025)

50 See Merle C. Ricklefs, Petrus Voorhoeve, and Annabel T. Gallop, *Indonesian Manuscripts in Great Britain: A Catalogue of Manuscripts in Indonesian Languages in British Public Collections* (Ecole française d’Extrême-Orient, 2014), 142.

resembles to a modern reader at first sight: a personal notebook in which a student of a foreign language writes down words learned and to be learned in an endeavour to systematize their knowledge. The vocabulary in question lies in-between those familiar genres, or rather comprises a lexicographical work of its own genre inherent in the cultural milieu and historical period it comes from. Even if initially compiled by a Malay-speaking learner of Arabic for private use and without any audiences in mind, this text certainly had an afterlife as a teaching and learning aid somewhere in West Sumatra's Islamic schools and study circles. In this educational milieu, it was read, discussed, and recopied along with other Arabic texts used as teaching materials—which largely explains the misspellings and divergences found in the two manuscripts as well as why interlinear arrangement was employed for a dictionary.

Containing not an authoritative Arabic text but a list of words compiled to be learnt and translated, the vocabulary still appears to manifest a hierarchy between the two languages—the source and the target ones, Arabic and Malay—in its layout: the Arabic words are bigger, bolder, and written by finer hand, while their Malay equivalents are smaller and scribbled chaotically in the spaces remaining between the lines. Yet it seems to be not only a perceived superiority of the language of the Qur'an over a vernacular that is reflected in the vocabulary, a work otherwise striving for certain equivalence between two languages, but also a hierarchy of a different kind—that between the text and paratext, the “black lines” of the *matn* and the “white spaces,” i.e., interlinear ones, filled with translation or annotation.⁵¹ Engaged in the same practices of transmission and consumption as other texts in Arabic used in Islamic education in the Indonesian-Malay world, *al-Jadwal fi kalām al-‘Arab* was apparently considered to reside in the same categories as those other texts: its Arabic and Malay components were not considered equal and inseparable, but were treated as the main text and auxiliary, explanatory notes. And in accordance with this distinction, different methods of transmission seem to have been applied to each.

As I have attempted to demonstrate in this article, the history of reproduction of the two copies of the vocabulary likely included both written and oral transmission, i.e., at different points in time the text might have been copied directly from a manuscript and at others written down by dictation. Various misspellings and discrepancies found in the Leiden manuscripts stem, therefore, not only from visual misinterpretations of letters and slips of pen by the scribe, but also from the “oral layers” between a source manuscript and its copy. In the case of the Arabic wordlist, which was considered the main text and thus was likely recopied directly from written sources, such an oral layer is limited to a few misspellings resulting from writing down by ear. As for the Malay translation below the line, it fell within the category of notes written down by students following the teacher's explanations—a sort of paratext open to improvement and modification—and thus appears to have been shaped by oral transmission to a much greater extent. Despite Van der Tuuk's distrust of the spoken word, orality still found its way into the manuscripts he collected.

The Arabic-Malay vocabulary that came down to us thanks to the Dutch lexicographer's studies and travels in Sumatra offers many interesting perspectives for inquiry. This article

51 See Mulaika Hijjas, “Marks of Many Hands. Annotation in the Malay Manuscript Tradition and a Sufi Compendium from West Sumatra,” *Indonesia and the Malay World* 45, no. 132 (2017): 246.

has only touched upon some of them. The two copies of the wordlist not only shed some light on the modes of such manuscripts' reproduction, but also reveal cultural and linguistic encounters within the Islamic world, i.e., between the Indonesian-Malay region and the Middle East—the encounters that unfold between the lines, in the interlinear spaces reserved for translation. Styled as a cosmography, attempting to describe the world around it in both the language of the scripture and the mother tongue, *al-Jadwal fi kalām al-ʿArab* provides an insight into the sociolinguistic microcosm of its compilers and their audiences, who likely belonged to the same Malay-speaking and Arabic-reading Islamic educational circles of 19th-century Sumatra.

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Illustrations

Fig. 1 Leiden Or. 3231, Leiden University Libraries, ff. 45r–44v.

Fig. 2 Leiden Or. 3233, Leiden University Libraries, ff. 37v–38r

Fig. 3 Leiden Or. 3231, Leiden University Libraries, ff. 28r–27v.

Fig. 4 Leiden Or. 3233, Leiden University Libraries, ff. 40v–41r.

Fig. 5 RAS Raffles Malay 75 (D), Royal Asiatic Society, ff. 152–153.

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